

Background, Contents, Aims of the Workshop

The workshop addresses two fundamental gaps in research on concepts that are plainly evident at the beginning of the 21st century. The first gap is between two groups of disciplines, which — at least in their more radical positions — disagree considerably not only about the relevant research questions but also about the nature and use of concepts. Cognitive science, psychology and parts of analytic philosophy focus on concepts as mental representations and offer theories as to their acquisition, possession and use. In other parts of analytic philosophy, concepts are conceived either as abstract objects or as abstractions of the uses of words, whereas history and philology often take concepts to be fundamentally related to text. Linguists, it seems, may fall on either side of the divide. The gap between the extreme positions of this spectrum appears so wide that it is questionable whether each respective research approach can be understood as being about concepts in a similar sense.

The question whether there is a concept of concept that would make all theories of concept be about some same concept has occasionally been raised. In philosophy, the question has found articulation in a recent overview offered by Chakrabarti and Siderits (2011, 15):

Unfortunately, like most frequently used words in a disputatious philosophical tradition, the word “concept” is so full of ambiguities that while all these theories are called “theories of concepts”, it is far from clear that they are trying to explicate the same concept of a concept. Some of these theories are concerned with what it is that we can do when we possess a concept and how we manifest such possession; others are concerned with what kind of mental representation a concept is; and yet others are interested mainly in the psychological story of how we acquire concepts. But can these theories even have different concepts of a *concept*, if they do not have, at some level, the same concept of concept?

In a contribution from the background of psychology and cognitive science, Slaney and Racine (2011, 81) point out that “there appears to be a higher order concept of ‘concept’ in which the ordinary, theoretical, and internalized senses [...] tend to feed”, but they are skeptical whether this could be extended to cover concept research in philosophy.

The issue has received less attention in history, philology and related disciplines, with the notable exception of some discussions in conceptual history and historical semantics (Busse, 1987; Palti, 2011). To the extent that such discussion has taken place at all, concepts have been understood as tightly related to language and, furthermore, to texts. Studying almost exclusively texts, it is no surprise that conceptual historians would emphasize words when thinking about concepts. Take, for example, the following statement by Dutt (2011, 41), concerning the premises of a conceptual history claimed to be valid across disciplines:

Concepts are formed in texts, and typically in a fashion, so that certain words, which are assigned as concept-words to concepts of relevance to the study, are used, or mentioned, in a series of connected statements. Definitions are only one (and surely not the most frequent) form of textually executed concept-formation — particularly not in philosophical contexts.

In the light of discussions about concepts in cognitive science, psychology and parts of philosophy, it would seem that those disciplines focused on the study of texts are also readily prone to assign the lieu and mechanism of concept-formation in texts. This finding, however, is obliquely mirrored by the disciplines which currently invest by far most resources and effort into conceptual research, namely cognitive science, psychology and analytic philosophy. Literature from these disciplines distinguishes itself by predominantly talking about the concepts of DOG, HORSE, CHAIR or the color RED, and often shies away from

tackling more complex concepts such as DEMOCRACY, MORALITY or MELANCHOLY, which are, it seems (at least in part, cf. Bickhard, 2011, 104), textually mediated and less amenable to empiricism and experimentation. Although language does play a major role in some of these theories, texts certainly do not. This is a pity, since research on concept acquisition, possession and use in these disciplines could very likely be profitably combined with discussion of concepts as encountered in or generated from texts. Of course, there are exceptions. Witness, for instance, the interesting work done on the concept DEMOCRACY in a radical empiricist manner, which looks at practices of democracy but also allows for a particular role of hearing or reading the word democracy as well as texts about democracy in individual concept-acquisition and formation (Prinz, 2005).

Against this background, the workshop seeks to cover new territory and to extend the existing discussions of the concept of concept (and their respective implications) to various strands of linguistics and philologies. The reasoning behind this is the following: if the gap between concepts as mental representations and concepts rooted in texts might be bridged at all, then the role of language is key and must be clarified. To the extent that language (and translation) is considered important in concept research, there is another gap in contemporary research on concepts, which regards natural languages. The second gap is best illustrated by considering which natural languages come to serve as examples in the existing research literature. These are almost exclusively Standard Average European (SAE) languages (Whorf 1939 [1956], Haspelmath 2001) spoken by speakers from white, educated, industrialized, rich, democratic (WEIRD) societies (Henrich, Heine & Norenzayan 2010), with some woefully recurring yet well-intended exceptions from single instances relating to Inuit or Hopi, or, indeed, the occasional extraterrestrial. It is at this juncture that the workshop hopes to contribute some new perspective to the existing discussions, by way of offering challenging cases from other languages (African, Chinese, Indian and Semitic languages, but also Old Irish), with a, presumably, different imagery.

The workshop will therefore bring together linguists, philosophers, and historians and scholars working in respective academic disciplines in African, Chinese, Indian, Japanese or Islamic Studies. However, the workshop will consciously try to eschew such disciplinary or areal divisions, in favor of an organization which addresses the common concerns expressed in the four following themes:

1. **Concept of concept:** What to make of the seemingly underlying circularity? What theories of concepts exist in different disciplines and do they speak to each other? Are they aware of or even explicitly addressing the observed circularity? Is CIRCULARITY the adequate concept to describe the problem? When Eco in his *The Infinity of Lists* draws on Russell's famous barber example to relate lists to set-theory and gives the example of a non-normal set where the set is an element of itself – “for example the set of all concepts is a concept” (2009, 396) – is he merely begging the question, since the “set of all concepts” is not a “concept” but a “set”? From another point of view, are there theories of concepts in non-European textual or oral traditions that may add to the theories under discussion, stemming from a European background? What is the textual and hermeneutic setting, from which such theories typically emerge?

2. **'Other' Concepts:** It is conspicuous that most research into concepts aims at nouns (e.g. NATURE, HORSE, CHAIR, and RELIGION). Some existing taxonomies distinguish kinds of concepts according to scope, listing exclusively nouns for examples: “We have concepts of readily observable states within ourselves, like PAIN; theoretically derived concepts, such as ELECTRON; and seemingly formal concepts, such as NUMBER. We have concepts of natural kinds, such as FROG; artifacts, such as BOAT; and social

kinds, such as MOTHER or DEMOCRACY” (Prinz, 2002, 3). Keeping in mind the notorious difficulty of defining a universal concept of word-class divisions (Haspelmath 2012, 2014 forthc.) in this section, we want to explore the possibility of tying concepts not to nouns, but to verbs (CLEANING, LAUGHING and CRYING, SQUEEZING THROUGH), or even to members of other word classes, such as NOW, WHY or AND. Not to be mistaken, there are existing taxonomies of concepts that would readily cover many of these challenges, e.g. distinguishing “comparative (x is heavier than y), quantitative (x weighs 20kg), individual (the author of *Atemschaufel*), logical (negation, implication), spatial and temporal concepts” and “predicative concepts,” the latter understood as “concepts that correspond to general terms of a particular kind, namely to the verbs, adjectives or count-nouns that feature in one-place predicates like ‘ x runs’, ‘ x is radioactive’ and ‘ x is a tool’” (Glock, 2011, 131). But what are the limits? What distinguishes an individual concept from a proper name, which according to some theories of concept would be precisely a candidate for what is *not* a concept? What ‘other’ concepts, including kinds of concepts, would the consideration of non-Standard Average European Languages and grammars and conceptual schemes based on them suggest?

3. ***The Imagery of Concepts:*** What metaphoric imagery do words used to talk about concepts in different languages express? What is the target domain of Chinese *gàiniàn* or *míng*? What of Sanskrit *vikalpa* and *tarkita* or Arabic *mashūm*? How do such terms relate to local theories of reference, abstraction or even persuasion? What happens, when words for *concept* are translated from one language to another, especially in cases of translation beyond the realm of genealogically or geographically related languages or language families? When does translation of terms for *concept* collapse in favor of either lexical innovation or mere transcription?

4. ***The Historicity of Concepts:*** In this section, we are not interested in different histories of particular concepts – with the exception of histories of the concept of concept – but in the question of the historicity of concepts as such. How to conceptualize conceptual change? Or is change confined to the level of word use, while concepts remain stable? If not, how to write a *Begriffsgeschichte* in the face of a concept of concept that itself is evolving?

A discussion across languages and disciplines is urgently needed since research has been moving towards understandings of concepts so different as to frustrate any common debate. It thus becomes increasingly difficult to draw on each other’s research or to contribute and formulate challenges that do not misfire from the beginning due to different conceptual premises. The goal of the workshop is to bring the different groups to the table and initiate a debate on how the different research efforts on concepts interlink or may be profitably juxtaposed to be mutually informing or challenging – while it is of course no less desirable to demarcate the limits of such common debate as precisely as possible.

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